

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**INFLUENCE OF COMORBID CONDITIONS ON TIMELY
ANTIBIOTIC DE-ESCALATION IN RESPIRATORY TRACT
INFECTIONS****Sharon Wilson¹, Tintu Thomas², Ancy Anil³, Angelin Ann Anil⁴, Dr. Elizabeth James⁵,
Abhilash Kumar⁶**^{1,2,3,4} PharmD Intern, Nazareth College of Pharmacy, Othara, Thiruvalla⁵ Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Believers Church Medical College Hospital, Thiruvalla⁶ Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Nazareth College of Pharmacy, Othara, Thiruvalla**Abstract:**

De-escalation generally refers to the process of reducing the spectrum of antibiotic therapy by either discontinuing unnecessary agents or switching to a narrower-spectrum antibiotic based on clinical response and microbiological data. Here we presents a study on Effect of comorbidities on De-Escalation of Antibiotics in Respiratory Tract Infections.

Keywords: Antibiotic De-escalation, RTIs, Comorbidities, KM -Curves

Corresponding author:

Sharon Wilson,
PharmD Intern,
Nazareth College of Pharmacy,
Othara, Thiruvalla

QR CODE

Please cite this article in press Sharon Wilson et al., *Influence Of Comorbid Conditions On Timely Antibiotic De-Escalation In Respiratory Tract Infections.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(08).

INTRODUCTION:

Antibiotic de-escalation is a key strategy in managing infections, particularly in serious respiratory tract infections. It involves initially prescribing broad-spectrum antibiotics that effectively cover a wide range of possible bacteria, ensuring the patient receives prompt and adequate treatment. Once laboratory results, such as culture and sensitivity tests, become available or the patient shows clinical improvement, healthcare providers reassess the antibiotic therapy.

At this point, the treatment is adjusted by switching to narrower-spectrum antibiotics that specifically target the identified bacteria or by stopping antibiotics if they are no longer necessary. This careful reduction in antibiotic use helps avoid unnecessary exposure to powerful drugs, which can cause side effects and increase healthcare costs. More importantly, antibiotic de-escalation plays a vital role in preventing the development of antibiotic resistance—a major public health concern where bacteria evolve to survive despite antibiotic treatment.^{1,2,3}

This approach not only benefits individual patients by providing effective and safer therapy but also contributes to preserving the effectiveness of antibiotics for the wider community. In patients with additional health conditions or comorbidities, antibiotic de-escalation requires particular attention to balance effective treatment and minimizing harm. Overall, it is a thoughtful and evidence-based method to optimize antibiotic use and combat the growing threat of antimicrobial resistance.^{4,5}

OBJECTIVE**RESULTS:****TABLE NO. 1: Distribution of comorbid conditions among patients**

SL.NO	COMORBIDITIES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1.	HYPERTENSION	150	23.47%
2.	T2DM	102	15.96%
3.	HEART DISEASE	91	14.24%
4.	DLP	59	9.23%
5.	RESPIRATORY DISEASE	46	7.20%
6.	CKD	38	5.95%
7.	CLD	33	5.16%
8.	OTHERS	70	10.95%

The Objective of this study was to to assess the de-escalation of antibiotics based on comorbid conditions

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY:

- **STUDY DESIGN** : A Retrospective Cohort Study.
- **STUDY SITE** : The study was done by collecting samples from Tertiary Care hospitals. The data was collected from medical records and patient drug charts. It was also obtained through Telephonic Communications. The medical records and patient drug charts were analyzed and telephonic interview were conducted for follow-up data on further events.
- **STUDY DURATION** : The study was conducted for a period of six months (November 2023 – April 2024).
- **SAMPLING METHOD** : Purposive Sample
- **SAMPLE SIZE** : All patients who met the inclusion criteria were included. The study population includes 571 patients.

Statistical formula for calculating sample size =

$$[Z^2 \times p(1-p) / e^2] / [1 + (Z^2 \times p(1-p) / e^2)N]$$

Where,

p = Standard Deviation

N = Population Size

e = Margin of error

Z = Z score

Inclusion Criteria: Patients above 18 years of age
Patients admitted to Medical

Wards

Exclusion Criteria: Patients admitted to Intensive care unit (ICU).

Pregnant women.

9.	NIL	50	7.82%
----	-----	----	-------

FIGURE NO. 1: Distribution of comorbid conditions among patients

It was observed from our study conducted on 571 patients that the commonly seen comorbid conditions were Hypertension seen in 150(23.47%) patients, Type 2 diabetes mellitus seen in 102 (16.46%) patients, Heart disease seen in 91 (14.24 %) patients, Dyslipidemia seen in 59(15.96%) patients, Respiratory disease (Asthma, COPD, Bronchitis) seen in 46(7.02%) patients, CKD seen in 38(5.95%) patients, CLD seen in 33(5.16 %) patients, other comorbid conditions like Seizure, Parkinsonism, Hypothyroidism, Rheumatoid arthritis, Psoriasis etc seen in 70 (10.95%) patients and no comorbidities seen in 50(7.82%) patients.

TABLE NO. 2: Distribution of past respiratory conditions with or without comorbidities

SL.NO	CHRONIC RESPIRATORY CONDITIONS	FREQUENCY	% Total
1.	With comorbidities	34	73.91%
2.	Without comorbidities	12	26.09%
	TOTAL	46	100%

FIGURE NO. 2: Distribution of past respiratory conditions with or without comorbidities

It was observed from our study conducted on 571 patients that there were 34(73.91%) patients that had past respiratory disease conditions like asthma, COPD, bronchitis with other comorbidities and 12(26.09%) patients that had past respiratory disease conditions without any other comorbidities.

FIGURE NO. 3: Distribution of KM- survival curve of time to de-escalation by comorbid conditions along with chronic respiratory conditions

The graph illustrates the time to de-escalation of continued antibiotic use based on certain comorbid conditions along with chronic respiratory conditions. Green curve shows people with a history of chronic respiratory conditions with other comorbidities (Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Hypertension, CKD, CLD, Heart disease etc), while the blue curve represents people with a previous history of Chronic respiratory conditions without comorbidities. Both groups exhibit steps in their curves, indicating changes in the probability over time. Results from statistical tests: Log-Rank Test: $p = 0.7$ and Wilcoxon Test: $p = 0.8$. The curves are close together suggests that the presence or absence of these comorbidities may not significantly impact de-escalation time.

FIGURE NO. 4: Distribution of KM- survival curve of time to de-escalation by comorbid conditions along without chronic respiratory condition

The graph represents the time to de-escalation for people without Chronic respiratory conditions with or without other comorbidities. Green Curve represents The people without any history of comorbidities and Blue curve represents the people with other comorbidities such as Type 2 Diabetes mellitus, Hypertension, Heart disease, Dyslipidaemia, CKD, CLD etc. The Log-Rank Test shows a p-value of 0.005, and the Wilcoxon Test has a p-value of 0.01, indicating significant differences between the two groups. These p-values suggest statistical significance in the observed differences between the two groups.

DISCUSSIONS

From our study on Antibiotic De-escalation in respiratory tract infections in the ward that out of 571 patients 521 patients had co-morbid conditions. Hypertension was seen in 100(17.51%) patients, Type 2 diabetes mellitus was seen in 94(16.46%) patients, heart disease was seen in 81(14.19%) patients, dyslipidemia was seen in 59(10.33%) patients, Respiratory disease(Asthma, COPD, Bronchitis) was seen in 46(8.06%) patients, CKD was seen in 38(6.65%) patients, CLD was seen in 33(5.78%) patients, other comorbid conditions like Seizure, Parkinsonism, Hypothyroidism, Rheumatoid arthritis, Psoriasis etc was seen in 70(12.26%) patients and no comorbidities was seen in 50(8.76%) patients. There were 34(73.91%) patients that had past respiratory disease conditions like asthma, COPD, bronchitis with other comorbidities and 12(26.09%) patients that had past respiratory disease conditions without any other comorbidities. A similar study was conducted by Prachi Tayal et.al, Antibiotics medication prescribed in the management of respiratory tract infection of tertiary care teaching hospital. The study was conducted in 111 people, in which majority of the patients had hypertension⁶.

Patient's with comorbidities took longer time for Antibiotic De-escalation than patients with no comorbidities as stated in a study conducted by Irene Rivero-Calle et.al, Lifestyle and comorbid conditions as risk factors for Community-Acquired Pneumonia in Outpatient Adults (NEUMO-ES-RISK project). In this study increased lifestyle and comorbid conditions has a great impact on the development of Respiratory Tract Infections^{7e}.

CONCLUSIONS:

Antibiotic de-escalation is a key component of Antimicrobial Stewardship Programs (ASPs). The presence of comorbidities significantly influences the timing of antibiotic de-escalation. In particular, patients with a history of respiratory conditions and other chronic illnesses tend to require a longer

duration before de-escalation is possible. Therefore, greater clinical attention should be directed towards these patients to ensure safe and timely adjustment of antibiotic therapy.

REFERENCES:

- 1) Shrestha J, Zahra F, Cannady J. Antimicrobial Stewardship [Internet]. PubMed. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2021. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK572068/>
- 2) Rupali P, Dtm&h, Frp. Introduction to antimicrobial stewardship and Principles of Antimicrobial prescribing [Internet]. Available from: https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/searo/essential-medicines/presentation-introduction-to-antimicrobial-stewardship-and-principles-of-antimicrobial-prescribing.pdf?sfvrsn=59bab377_1
- 3) Fishman N. Antimicrobial Stewardship. *The American Journal of Medicine*. 2006 Jun;119(6): S53–61.
- 4) Dellit TH, Owens RC, McGowan JE, Gerding DN, Weinstein RA, Burke JP, et al. Infectious Diseases Society of America and the Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America Guidelines for Developing an Institutional Program to Enhance Antimicrobial Stewardship. *Clinical Infectious Diseases* [Internet]. 2007 Jan 15;44(2):159–77. Available from: <https://academic.oup.com/cid/article/44/2/159/328413>
- 5) Prachi Tayal et al, “ Antibiotics medication prescribed in the management of respiratory tract infection of tertiary care teaching hospital”, *Journal of Young Pharmacists* 13(3):262-266 ,DOI:10.5530/jyp.2021.13.53
- 6) Rivero-Calle I, Cebeý-López M, Pardo-Seco J, Yuste J, Redondo E, Vargas DA, Mascarós E, Díaz-Maroto JL, Linares-Rufo M, Jimeno I, Gil A, Molina J, Ocaña D, Martínón-Torres F. Lifestyle and comorbid conditions as risk factors for community-acquired pneumonia in outpatient adults (NEUMO-ES-RISK project). *BMJ Open Respir Res*. 2019 Mar 12;6(1):e000359. doi: 10.1136/bmjresp-2018-000359. PMID: 31178994; PMCID: PMC6530500.
- 7) Murray CJ, Ikuta KS, Sharara F, Swetschinski L, Aguilar GR, Gray A, Han C, Bisignano C, Rao P, Wool E, Johnson SC. Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis. *The lancet*. 2022 Feb 12;399(10325):629-55.

- 8) Das S. Haque I, Gaur A, Suhail Mustafa M. de-escalation pattern of antibiotics in the medical intensive care unit of a tertiary care hospital in north India. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2020 Jan 9:1451-1460
- 9) WHO EMRO | What is the difference between antibiotic and antimicrobial resistance? | Antimicrobial resistance | Health topics [Internet]. www.emro.who.int. Available from: <https://www.emro.who.int/health-topics/drug-resistance/what-is-the-difference-between-antibiotic-and-antimicrobial-resistance.html>
- 10) Britannica. Antibiotic | chemical compound. In: Encyclopedia Britannica [Internet]. 2019. Available from: <https://www.britannica.com/science/antibiotic>
- 11) Aminov RI. A brief history of the antibiotic era: lessons learned and challenges for the future. Frontiers in microbiology. 2010 Dec 8; 1:134. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3109405/>
- 12) Ullah H, Ali S. Classification of Anti-Bacterial Agents and Their Functions [Internet]. www.intechopen.com. IntechOpen; 2017. Available from: <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/55303>
- 13) Antimicrobial Resistance Collaborators. Global Burden of Bacterial Antimicrobial Resistance in 2019: A Systematic Analysis. The Lancet [Internet]. 2022 Jan 19;399(10325):629–55. Available from: [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(21\)02724-0/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(21)02724-0/fulltext)